

Table 3. Mean squares and *F* test for additional sum of squares corresponding to N sources.

Source of additional sum of squares	Parameter	Mean square ^a
USG	δ2η2	0.785
UIU	δ3η3	0.015
NCU	δ4η4	0.010
PCU	δ5η5	1.175**
RPCU	δ6η6	0.005
Error	σ2	0.27
	(df)	12

^a** = significant at the 0.01 level.

including parameters δ_{η_i} = 2 to 6, in FTM is given in Table 3.

The significant regression coefficients d₅ h₅ indicate that the response curves of PCU and urea are different. The values d₅ > b₁ and h₅ = c₁ indicate that the response of rice to the N in PCU was larger than to that in PU. The effect of PCU was greater than that of all other sources tried.

Carryover effects of N on the succeeding northeast monsoon crop depended on the source of N. PCU at 112.5 kg N/ha had the most carryover effect. The least carryover effects were with RPCU, NCU, UIU, and PU.

Total grain yield for both seasons was highest with PCU at 112.5 kg N/ha in the first crop and PU at 45 kg N/ha in the second crop. ■

Effect of N source on irrigated rice yield in Cameroon

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Irrigated rice has been grown in Ndop Plain, Western Cameroon, since the early 1970s without any specific fertilizer recommendation. To fertilize their rice crops, most farmers use a 20-10-10 complex recommended for coffee.

We compared the effect on rice yield of three locally available N-fertilizer products (urea, diammonium phosphate (DAP), 20-10-10 complex) applied as basal, followed by urea or ammonium sulfate (AS) topdressed during 1987-89 wet seasons (mid-Jul to mid-Dec).

Experimental soil was Tropaquept, clay loam texture, pH 5.1, 3.08% organic C, 0.23% total N, 4.5 ppm available P (Bray 1), 39% base saturation, CEC 16.6 meq/100 g, 4.12 meq/100 g Ca, 1.63 meq/100 g Mg, and 0.67 meq/100 g K (NH₄OAc extractable). N (80 kg/ha) was

applied in three equal splits: basal, 21 d after transplanting (DT), and at panicle initiation. A common 26 kg P, 33 kg K/ha were applied as triple super-phosphate and muriate of potash. P and K rates were adjusted for the amount of P and K applied with DAP and 20-10-10. Basal fertilizers were broadcast and incorporated before transplanting rice. Fertilizer was topdressed by broadcasting in plots with 5-6 cm standing water, followed by hand stirring into the soil.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Four-wk-old seedlings of IR7167-33-2-3 were transplanted in 20-m² plots at 25 × 15-cm spacing 2 d after basal fertilizer application. The plots were continuously flooded from transplanting to the late dough stage. A 12.56-m² area in the middle of each plot, leaving two border rows on all sides, was harvested for yield measurements.

N treatments did not differ significantly in two of the three years (see table).

DAP applied basal followed by urea or ammonium sulfate topdressing gave the highest yields. ■

Effect of neem extract-coated urea on rice yield and nitrogen use efficiency of transplanted rice

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We evaluated prilled urea (PU) and neem extract-coated urea (NECU) at 90, 120, and 150 kg N/ha during 1988-89 wet seasons. Urea was coated with neem extract in 100:1 ratio on weight basis. Experimental soil was a deep black Vertisol, with pH 7.7, 0.6% organic C, 25.1 kg available Olsen's P/ha, 240.7 kg available K/ha, and 0.2 ppm available Zn.

Half the PU was incorporated before transplanting and half in equal topdressings at tillering and panicle initiation. NECU was applied half before transplanting and half at tillering. All plots received 26.4 kg P, 33.2 kg K/ha. Rice variety Jaya was transplanted at 20 × 10-cm spacing, 3 seedlings/hill.

Grain yield was significantly higher with 150 kg N/ha applied as NECU in

Grain yield of irrigated rice as affected by nitrogen source. Ndop Plain, Cameroon. 1987-89 wet seasons.^a

Treatment ^b			N rate (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)			
Basal	Topdress 1	Topdress 2		1987	1988	1989	Mean
None	None	None	0	2.5	4.6	5.1	4.1
Urea	Urea	Urea	80	3.4	6.0	6.7	5.4
20-10-10	AS	Urea	80	3.5	5.5	6.3	5.1
20-10-10	Urea	Urea	80	3.9	5.5	5.4	4.9
DAP	AS	Urea	80	4.3	5.8	6.9	5.7
DAP	Urea	Urea	80	4.3	6.2	6.9	5.8
LSD (0.05)				1.0	0.8	0.8	
CV (%)				18.1	10.0	8.4	

^aAv of 4 replications. ^bAS = ammonium sulfate.

Influence of NECU and PU on grain yield and number of productive tillers. Kota India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		Mean productive tillers (no./m ²)
	1988	1989	
Control (no N)	3.6	3.5	214.0
90 kg N/ha, PU	5.0	5.0	284.0
120 kg N/ha, PU	5.7	5.6	294.6
150 kg N/ha, PU	6.0	5.9	318.6
90 kg N/ha, NECU	5.7	5.7	292.1
120 kg N/ha, NECU	6.0	5.9	306.0
150 kg N/ha, NECU	6.3	6.3	335.9
LSD (0.05)			
	0.4	0.3	20.1